

Supplementary Information:

Imaging Orbital Vortex Lines in Three-Dimensional Momentum Space

T. Figgemeier,* M. Ünzelmann,† J. Schusser, B. Geldiyev, P. Kagerer, and F. Reinert

Experimentelle Physik VII and Würzburg-Dresden Cluster of Excellence ct.qmat,

Universität Würzburg, Am Hubland, D-97074 Würzburg, Germany

P. Eck,* L. Crippa, and G. Sangiovanni

ITPA and Würzburg-Dresden Cluster of Excellence ct.qmat,

Universität Würzburg, Am Hubland, D-97074 Würzburg, Germany

J. N. Neu and T. Siegrist

Department of Chemical and Biomedical Engineering,

FAMU-FSU College of Engineering Tallahassee, FL 32310, USA and

National High Magnetic Field Laboratory, Tallahassee, FL 32310, USA

J. Buck and M. Källäne

Institut für Experimentelle und Angewandte Physik,

Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, D-24098 Kiel, Germany and

Ruprecht Haensel Laboratory, Kiel University and DESY, Germany

M. Hoesch

Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY, D-22607 Hamburg, Germany

K. Rosnagel

Institut für Experimentelle und Angewandte Physik,

Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, D-24098 Kiel, Germany

Ruprecht Haensel Laboratory, Kiel University and DESY, Germany and

Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY, D-22607 Hamburg, Germany

L.-K. Lim

Zhejiang Institute of Modern Physics,

Department of Physics, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou,

Zhejiang 310027, People's Republic of China

R. Moessner

*Max Planck Institute for the Physics of Complex Systems
and Würzburg-Dresden Cluster of Excellence ct.qmat,
Noethnitzer Strasse 38, D-01187 Dresden, Germany*

D. Di Sante

*Department of Physics and Astronomy,
University of Bologna, I-40136 Bologna, Italy*

H. Bentmann

*Experimentelle Physik VII and Würzburg-Dresden Cluster of Excellence ct.qmat,
Universität Würzburg, Am Hubland, D-97074 Würzburg, Germany and
Center for Quantum Spintronics, Department of Physics,
NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology, NO-7491 Trondheim, Norway*

(Dated: October 10, 2024)

* These authors contributed equally to the present work.

† These authors contributed equally to the present work.; muenzelmann@physik.uni-wuerzburg.de

CONTENTS

Supplementary Note 1: Additional data analysis of the nodal line	4
Supplementary Note 2: Complementary dichroism data	8
Supplementary Note 3: Model for the orbital vortex line	10
Supplementary Note 5: In-plane OAM texture: DFT and CD	13
References	15

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 1: ADDITIONAL DATA ANALYSIS OF THE NODAL LINE

Detailed analysis of the band dispersion and energy splitting around the nodal point

In this section, we provide an additional analysis of the almost movable Weyl nodal line (am-WNL). Fig. S1a shows a high-resolution SX-ARPES spectrum taken at a photon energy of $h\nu = 618$ eV, which corresponds to a $\Gamma\Sigma$ cut in the 3D bulk Brillouin zone of TaAs. Several energy distribution curves around the crossing point were fitted by the sum of two Gaussians including a Fermi-Dirac distribution and a linear background. The resulting peak positions are plotted as green and orange dots in Fig. S1a. From this, we can calculate the energy splitting ΔE of the two spin branches which is plotted in Fig. S1b as a function of k_x . For wave vectors in the range of $|k_x| \approx 0.6 \dots 0.9 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ we find $\Delta E \propto |k_x|$ allowing for linear interpolation of the a detailed position of the crossing point which yields $q_0 = (0.76 \pm 0.05) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$.

Figure S1. **Detailed analysis of the high-resolution SX-ARPES spectra.** **a** SX-ARPES spectrum recorded at $h\nu = 618$ eV corresponding to an $k_z = 0$ plane. The green and orange dots indicate the peak position of the two spin branches received through fitting EDCs. **b** Energy splitting of the spin branches obtained from **a**. Open and filled markers represent the splitting for positive and negative k_x , respectively. The energy splitting is linear in k around the nodal point as shown by the fit corresponding fit (solid line).

Determination of the k_z - and energy-dependent undulation of the nodal point

In order to trace the nodal line within the $k_z k_x$ mirror planes (see Fig. 2d in the main text), we recorded SX-ARPES spectra using different photon energies $h\nu = 618\dots 673$ eV in steps of $\Delta h\nu = 5$ eV. Given the long acquisition time needed to obtain data in high resolution and sufficient statistics allowing for a detailed fitting procedure explained in the previous section, we determined the in-plane wave vector $q_{0,x}$ of the band crossing points in three different manners. This is shown in Fig. S2 for two exemplary photon energies of $h\nu = 638$ eV and $h\nu = 663$ eV.

First, we analyzed the k_x -dependent modulation of the photoemission intensity I , which is likely induced by the change of orbital character at the crossing point, as outlined in the main text. In Fig. S2a,d we show the symmetrized data sets $I(+k_x) + I(-k_x)$, which clearly reveal abrupt changes by following the intensity as a function of k_x . Taking the center height of the step-like function $I(k_x)$, we determine the wave vectors $q_{0,x}$ marked by the dashed red lines.

In the second case (Fig. S2b,d), we extracted the crossing point from the second derivative of the photoemission intensity $I_{2\text{nd}} \propto \frac{\partial^2 I(k_x, E)}{\partial k_x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 I(k_x, E)}{\partial E^2}$, which can enhance the visibility of fine structures even in more broad features of ARPES-spectra. Again, the estimated wave vectors are indicated by the red dashed lines.

In the last case, we were considering the Linear Dichroism (LD), which is sensitive to the k_x -dependent complex phase $i\gamma(k_x)$ (see main text) and accordingly orbital angular momentum (OAM) L_y in the initial state. In particular, L_y changes its sign at the position of the nodal line and we use this to determine its $k_z(k_x)$ evolution as exemplary shown in Fig. S2c,f.

Taken together, we determined the undulation of the nodal line in three-dimensional momentum space using three distinct methods. The result is shown in Fig. 2d in the main text proofing a reasonable agreement for all three approaches and overall excellent agreement with the DFT calculation.

Interestingly, we find that the nodal line does not only undulate as a function of momentum but — given the k_z -dispersion of the bulk bands in TaAs — also the energy of the crossing point changes. In Fig. S3, we show the experimentally determined energy as a function of k_z in comparison to the corresponding DFT calculation. The reasonable agreement between experimental data and calculation further underpins the reliability of our data analysis.

Figure S2. **Exemplary data sets for the determination of the undulation of the nodal point.** Spectra in **a-c** are taken at $h\nu = 638$ eV ($k_z \approx 0.382\pi/c$) and in **d-f** at $h\nu = 663$ eV ($k_z \approx 0.842\pi/c$). For each photon energy, the position of the nodal point has been determined in three different ways (see text) as shown in (a,d), (b,e), and (c,f). In extracted wave vector \mathbf{q}_0 is marked by the dashed line in each case.

Figure S3. **Binding energy undulation of the nodal point.** Data points represent the experimental values extracted from the photon energy series (partially) shown in Fig. 2a of the main part. The solid line represents the binding energy undulation obtained by our DFT calculation (see Fig. 2b in the main part).

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 2: COMPLEMENTARY DICHROISM DATA

In Fig. S4, we compare the LD (both measured and for the one-step calculation) at different photon energies which correspond to an equivalent out-of-plane momentum, i.e. $k_z \approx 0$. For both $h\nu$ we find an overall reasonable agreement and, in particular, the important sign change at the WNL. As pointed out in the main manuscript, a deviation between theory and experiment is the appearance of a surface feature in the calculation, denoted as “S” in Fig. S4(c) and (e). Owing to the existence of several approximations to shape the surface barrier [1], all of which fulfill the expected $1/z$ asymptotics, the energetics and momentum dependence of the surface states emerging from its existence can take different shapes [2]. The choice of a modeled surface barrier with given parameters should then be done so that it reflects the real physical experiment as well as possible. Surface states in addition to surface resonances are sensitive to the shape of the potential barrier and their description requires detailed comparison to experiment within our computational approach. However, surface states (and resonances) play a negligible role concerning the bulk states discussed in our manuscript. This stems from the fact that the corresponding observables of the photoemission experiment of the bulk states remain unaltered by the given shape of the surface potential. This consequently implies that as long as the corresponding bulk state is present, the calculation correctly captures the underlying wavefunction properties. The high reliability of SPR-KKR in modeling physical systems and their initial state properties of bulk states has been demonstrated elsewhere, see, e.g., Ref. [3].

Figure S4. **Linear dichroism at different photon energies.** **a,c** Experimental and calculated LD at $h\nu = 618$ eV corresponding to $k_z \approx 0$ (see main text). **d,e** Equivalent equi- k_z cut measured and calculated using a photon energy of 433 eV.

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 3: MODEL FOR THE ORBITAL VORTEX LINE

A generic Hamiltonian describing the spin-split electronic structure in TaAs can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{k}) = \mathcal{H}_0(\mathbf{k}) + \mathcal{H}_{\text{ISB}}(\mathbf{k}) + \mathcal{H}_{\text{SOC}} , \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{H}_0(\mathbf{k})$ describes the unperturbed system and $\mathcal{H}_{\text{ISB}}(\mathbf{k})$ and \mathcal{H}_{SOC} the influence of inversion symmetry breaking and spin-orbit coupling, respectively. In this section, we will explain the hierarchical formation of the orbital vortex line (OVL) and am-WNL.

We start with the symmetry analysis of the k -dependent terms. ISB leads to the formation of OAM and one can write $\mathcal{H}_{\text{ISB}}(\mathbf{k}') = \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{k}') \cdot \mathbf{L}$, where \mathbf{k}' is relative to the TRIM, i.e., the N-point in TaAs. Time-reversal symmetry implies $\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{k}') = -\mathbf{d}(-\mathbf{k}')$ and considering the $k_y = 0$ plane, M_y mirror symmetry gives $d_x = d_z = 0$, i.e., the OAM is aligned completely along L_y . Together, one finds $d_y(k'_x, 0, k'_z) = -d_y(-k'_x, 0, -k'_z)$. Importantly, this implies that for any path within the $k_x k_z$ plane connecting the points $(\pm k'_x, 0, \pm k'_z)$ (see Fig. 4 in the main text), there has to be one wave vector where the OAM L_y is zero and switches its sign. This in turn means that there must be a closed line, where $d_y(\mathbf{q}_0) = 0$. This is the OAM-zero line found in our DFT calculation and LD measurements (see Fig. 4(b,c) in the main text).

In order to show that this is related to the formation of an OVL, we consider a linearized Hamiltonian around this point $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{q}_0$:

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{OVL}}(\mathbf{q}) = \mathcal{H}_0(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{q}) \cdot \mathbf{L} . \quad (2)$$

Applying mirror symmetry M_y , one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} d_x(q_x, q_y, q_z) &= -d_x(q_x, -q_y, q_z) , \\ d_y(q_x, q_y, q_z) &= +d_y(q_x, -q_y, q_z) , \\ d_z(q_x, q_y, q_z) &= -d_z(q_x, -q_y, q_z) . \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

and in lowest order in q , one can derive

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{ISB}}(\mathbf{q}) \approx -\alpha_{y,x} q_y L_x + (\alpha_{x,y} q_x - \alpha_{z,y} q_z) L_y + \alpha_{y,z} q_y L_z , \quad (4)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha_{x,y} &= \alpha_x \cos \theta_z \\
\alpha_{y,x} &= \alpha_y \cos \theta_z \\
\alpha_{z,y} &= \alpha_z \sin \theta_z \\
\alpha_{y,z} &= \alpha_y \sin \theta_z .
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Here, the parameters $\alpha_{x,y,z}$ quantify the ISB strength in the respective momentum direction and θ_z is the angle of the tangent to the nodal line at \mathbf{q}_0 , with respect to the k_z direction. The latter is an additional parameter measuring the undulation of the movable nodal line not fixed by symmetry.

The orbital vortex structure circulating the nodal line necessarily gives rise to tilting of the winding plane of OAM whenever $\theta_z \neq 0$. For our case, the winding plane is fixed by two perpendicular orbital angular momentum components, namely, L_y and $\cos \theta_z L_x - \sin \theta_z L_z$, which is evolving as we move along the nodal line. The two corresponding momenta locked with the OAM components are $(\cos \theta_z q_x - \sin \theta_z q_z)$ and $-q_y$, respectively, to ensure a winding $\nu = +1$. We therefore arrive at the form (4) taking the tilting into account.

This analysis shows how symmetries in TaAs enforce the formation of the OVL. The characteristic pseudospin vortex texture appears from those terms acting on the orbital subspace. The formation of a two-fold degenerate Weyl nodal line in turn requires the presence of spin-orbit coupling (SOC). In a local picture, latter expresses as $\mathcal{H} = \lambda_{\text{SOC}} \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{S}$, which causes (anti)-parallel alignment of OAM and spin \mathbf{S} and the lifting of spin-degeneracy in the OAM-carrying bands. Neglecting interband SOC, one can write the effective interband Hamiltonian of a band Ψ as

$$\mathcal{H}_{\Psi}(\mathbf{q}) \approx \lambda_{\text{SOC}} \langle \mathbf{L} \rangle_{\Psi} \cdot \mathbf{S} , \tag{6}$$

with the OAM expectation values $\langle \mathbf{L} \rangle_{\Psi}$ derived from Eq. 2 and Eq. 4.

It immediately follows that the OVL with $\langle L \rangle = 0$ in the vortex core leads to an effective suppression of SOC at \mathbf{q}_0 , $\mathcal{H}_{\Psi}(\mathbf{q}_0) = 0$. As such, the OVL serves as a protection of the band degeneracy against SOC. The symmetry-enforced emergence of the OVL thus precedes the formation of the am-WNL.

Our model analysis is completely in line with a precise symmetry analysis in Ref. [4], in which the occurrence of the am-WNL has been theoretically predicted. Furthermore, our finding of a pseudospin vortex sheds light on the hierarchy of distinct terms in the Hamiltonian (Eq. 1). In particular, the topological orbital texture exists even without SOC, i.e., in the absence of the nodal

line. This is also confirmed in our DFT calculation shown in Fig. S5b. Although SOC is absent, the OAM in the band switches its sign at \mathbf{q}_0 .

Even though we cannot switch off SOC in the real experiment, our one-step photoemission calculations yield nearly identical LD textures near the am-WNL q_0 , regardless of the presence of SOC (see Figs. S5d,e).

Figure S5. **Influence of SOC on the OAM and LD texture.** (a,b) OAM-projected DFT band structure calculations in the $k_z = 0$ -plane with (a) and without (b) SOC. In both cases, an OAM sign change is observed at \mathbf{q}_0 confirming the OAM texture is independent from the presence of SOC. c Experimentally observed and d,e corresponding calculated LD at $h\nu = 618$ eV. The one-step photoemission calculations allow for switching of SOC as shown in e. The occurrence of the LD sign change at \mathbf{q}_0 does likewise not depend on the presence of SOC.

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 5: IN-PLANE OAM TEXTURE: DFT AND CD

Comparison between CD and DFT

For comparison with the experimentally reconstructed in-plane OAM texture shown in Fig. 4d,e in the main text, the corresponding constant energy cuts obtained from the DFT Wannier model are shown in Fig. S6a,b. Overall there is a good qualitative agreement between experimental data and calculation. In particular, for both we observe an OAM winding around the nodal points for both considered out-of-plane momenta. This becomes even more apparent in the close-up maps around the momenta $\mathbf{q}_{\parallel} = (0, k_y = 0.93 \text{ \AA}^{-1})$ at $k_z = 0.58 2\pi/c$ shown in Fig. S6c,d. Here, panel c corresponds to the experimental data (i.e., close-up from the data in Fig. 4e in the main text) and (d) to the calculation. The color code in the left and right panels represents the $n\text{CD}_{0^\circ}$ (L_x) and $n\text{CD}_{90^\circ}$ (L_y) both changing sign at the nodal point along q_y and q_x , respectively. In combination, we can observe a rotating vortex-like vector field around \mathbf{q}_0 .

Figure S6. **In-plane OAM texture obtained from DFT and CD.** (a,b) Constant energy cuts (CECs) obtained from the DFT-based Wannier model at $k_z = 0$ (a) and $k_z = 0.58 2\pi/c$ (b) at the energy of the respective nodal point. The color code in (a,b) represents L_x and the vectors reflect the in-plane OAM texture. (c,d) Zoom-in around a nodal point at $k_z = 0.58 2\pi/c$ and $(q_x = 0, q_y = 0) = (k_x = 0, k_y = 0.93 \text{ \AA}^{-1})$.

-
- [1] J. Rundgren and G. Malmstrom, *Journal of Physics C: Solid State Physics* **10**, 4671 (1977).
- [2] A. Bendounan, K. Aït-Mansour, J. Braun, J. Minár, S. Bornemann, R. Fasel, O. Gröning, F. Sirotti, and H. Ebert, *Phys. Rev. B* **83**, 195427 (2011).
- [3] S. Beaulieu, J. Schusser, S. Dong, M. Schüler, T. Pincelli, M. Dendzik, J. Maklar, A. Neef, H. Ebert, K. Hricovini, et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **125**, 216404 (2020).
- [4] M. M. Hirschmann, A. Leonhardt, B. Kilic, D. H. Fabini, and A. P. Schnyder, *Phys. Rev. Materials* **5**, 054202 (2021).